

An Artful Approach of Different Electronics & Instruments Based On Indian Vedic Techniques

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Abstract:

This paper is focused on the different Vedic period instruments; especially electronics-based instruments. Also a correlation has been performed between Vedic period instruments with the modern time instruments and the technology behind that. Here, a brief discussion has been made for the instruments used in the fields of electronics, electrical, nuclear, biomedical, telecommunication, embedded system, artificial intelligence, robotics, aerospace, and agriculture during that Vedic period, and their connection with the similar modern instruments has been established in a smoothening way. This paper is an approach to deliver the information about the vast areas of Vedic knowledge and its contribution towards the latest electronics-based instruments and hence towards the world developments which can never be expressed in just these few pages. Still, through this paper, the authors are trying to convey information about the beauty of the Vedic era Indian instruments which were much more advanced logically and technologically than the rest of the world during those Vedic periods. Authors are also outlining the finest part of the primitive Indian instruments having the least negative effects on the society, environment, and on the earth as compared to modern instruments which is only goal-oriented and not much focus on its side effects.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Bhaskaracharya, Data Transmission, Satellite, Brahmastra, Nuclear Instrumentation, Robotics, Maxwell, Vasistha, Dry Cell, Aryabhata, Sanjay, Sushruta Samhita, Vaimanika Shastra, Agastya Samhita

1. INTRODUCTION

Vedas, the “Knowledge Power-house” is the real treasure for all the science and technology development of the modern world. Max Mullar has rightly quoted that the origin of Vedas is older than the writings of Egyptians and the Nenaheys. Weber analyzed that the written format of the ancient literature is enormous in India then compares to the rest of the world [1]. Veda gives information about different instruments and methods used in the filled of biomedical, Aircraft technology, communication, automation, nuclear, and many more in the Vedic period [1]. Based on Vedic knowledge, and correlating this Vedic information, a huge area of research has been introduced newly in the field of engineering during this on-going modern period. This new area is known as Vedic Engineering. The detailed descriptions of Vedic engineering and other areas whose base parts are placed completely on Vedic knowledge have given in detail below.

2. VEDIC ENGINEERING

Veda which is written thousands of years ago, deals with the branch of science and technology, concerned with the design, measurements, buildings, use of different instruments, and structures called as Vedic Engineering. Vedic engineering is a high-quality treasure of knowledge in the shape of Vedas, Upanishads & Samhita's [2]. Ancient Munis and Rishis have proved various scientific theories, laws and principles which are majorly based on Vedic engineering for more than thousands of years ago. There are so many verses in Vedic literature that specify the speculation of the universe, Medicine, Life sciences, Instrumentation, Astrology, Metallurgy, Chemistry, Telegraphy, and Engineering. The world must always remain grateful to those great, prominent, eminent Rishis who founded and established a root of knowledge in the shape of Vedas & Upanishads and scattered this expertise throughout this world whenever people needed it [3].

3. DESCRIPTIONS OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY IN VEDA.

Veda is an ocean of knowledge whose knowledge depth can't be described in just a couple of pages. It has an infinite boundary of knowledge. So before proceeding further, let discuss a few correlation of Veda for science and technology as per the need [4].

- I. **Rig Veda** discusses about planets (There are a lot of stars, the solar system's gravitational effect makes the earth stable, the earth continues to revolve on its axle) electromagnetic effects, mass and energy conservation, measurement of time and many more [5].
- II. **Atharvaveda** discusses electricity generation, spacecraft and seven colors in the Sun and many more.
- III. **Ayurveda** concerns biomedical instrumentation, medicine, and health issues, planet science and many more.
- IV. **Sama Veda** says about the Sun never sets or rises and it is the earth, which rotated.
- V. **Sthapatya** explains about architecture
- VI. **Markandeya Purana** explains earth is flattened at the poles.

3.1 Electronics and Instrumentation in the Vedic period.

As this paper primarily focuses on electronics and instrumentation engineering in the Vedic period, hence to understand the entire concept, the following points should be discussed.

3.1.1 Digital Electronics in Veda

Vedas gave us the knowledge of the existence of the whole universe from Shunya. A scholar and mathematician named **Brahmagupta**, first time defined zero written as "Shunya" and its operation in AD 628 and also developed a symbol as a "dot underneath the numbers" for it. Also by using zero, he had written rules for mathematical operations like addition and subtraction. The Hindu genius **Bhaskaracharya** proved that any number divided by 0 is infinity and that infinity however divided remains infinity [6]. Then, **Aryabhatta** a great mathematician and an astronomer used zero in the decimal system and he also gave the concept of the number system [7]. The concept of "0" that is shunya & "1" that is one or singularity is discussed in the Vedic period. Now, whole digital electronics, graphics of games, and all the computations are the game of 1 and 0s? Just because electronics cannot go without 0 and 1, it is the most relatable branch of Science to the Science of Vedas because the base for them is unknowingly the same [8].

3.1.2 Communication Theory in Veda

Many Vedic scriptures tell that saints in ancient times could attain a siddhi by whose means they could communicate to people at a distance this was known as telepathy [9]. Look today we have cell phones; internet and pagers to do the work-related that we have achieved what was mentioned in Vedas.

3.1.2.1 Data transmission concept

Modern technocrats are dealing with wired or wireless data transmission. Wi-Fi connectivity, the emergence of Bluetooth, growth in the satellite connectivity and VoIP are some emerging trends of the modern IT world in data transmission. At the time of the Vedic period, the common figure of Lord Narada was the perfect example of the data transmission medium in Vedic scriptures. These Demigods, Rishis, and yogis possessed some special powers through the regular recitation of Mantra [9].

3.1.2.2 Dual Mode Signal Generator or Receptor (Sanjay's Equipment)

This data transmission mechanism possessed dual-mode signal generators. It also looks that the satellite connectivity was very much there. The sending/receiving transponders of the Sanjay's set were directly linked through satellites and these satellites were focused on the battlefield of Kurukshetra (Fig.1). It may be another possibility that the equipment possessed by the Sanjay may be a dual-mode signal transmission and receptivity. This equipment may be firstly focused on the activity area, generates the signal with the help of satellite connectivity, or through the auto generator mechanism, then sending the signals back to the same device and act as a receiver of the signal in the live audio and visual format. Just imagine the equipment's data transmission features and data storing capacity. It must have covered the concept of camera focusing, frame drops, enormous data movement during data transmission, linking failures, and real-time signals generations.

Fig.1: Sanjay's data transmission with the blind king Dhritarashtra [10]

Some Key features of Sanjay's equipment are

- I) Camera-based technology
- II) Auto-focusing and independent of human being
- III) Real-time Signal generator transponders
- IV) Signal buffering and storage facility
- V) Signal receiver antenna and receptor transponder
- VI) Signal broadcaster with live impact
- VII) Connectivity with available satellite technology
- VIII) Hi-end data connectivity

IX) Wireless data transmission

X) Data transmission control through the human mind

Apart from the above technical features, some emotional features were also included in Sanjay's Vision Tool-Camera, like-Interpretation of activities, analysis of Wrong and right, and advising his Master fearlessly [10].

3.1.3 Embedded System in Veda: (Chitragupta – The supercomputer with high microprocessor)

Veda clearly speaks to say that the human brain has infinite memory and its range and speed are limitless. Electronics had developed the first microprocessor and microcontroller keeping the human brain as a reference. Ancient scriptures do quote about a Hindu demigod Chitragupta who works under the supervision of the God of death and justice called Yamraj and has assigned the task of keeping a complete history of actions of millions of people, creatures from death to birth on this earth. After their death, deciding as regards sending them to heaven or hell fully depending on their actions on this earth's surface. Rig Veda told this Chitragupta as a perfect professional. This is known as "Akashic Records" in theosophical parlance. The "Chitragupta" must possess the amazing capacity of handling multiple files of the millions of creatures on this earth. Just think of that supercomputer's immense memory, enormous storage capacity, and amazing microprocessor. The activities (karma) and the resultants (karmafals) are just storing flawless with a separate data dictionary for every person on this earth [11]. It must be a voluminous database, where millions of data extraction and data mining activities are happening in a fraction of nanosecond. Millions of files are moving so fast to and fro from the secondary storage to the main memory of this computer. Just imagine the wonderful data connectivity and the top-class data security of the God's computer. Small comparison of Chitragupta with modern computers is as follows:

Modern computers	Chitraguta–The supercomputer with high microprocessor
Memory varies as per utility.	Enormous Memory –supernatural memory.
Multiprocessing, multitasking.	Handling millions of activities in sequence.
Programmed for specific purpose.	Programmed for natural and supernatural process
Data extraction depends on the Database structure and media.	Data extraction is independent of all the media and structure of the database.
Limit of multiple file handling.	No limitation of file handling issue.
Processor is in the development stage.	Perfect processor.

The threat of viruses cyber-security is an issue cyber laws govern activities.	No threats of viruses are a full proof security Supernatural law governs the activities.
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3.1.4 Nuclear Instrumentation in Veda

Vedas gives knowledge about very powerful weapons one of which is Brahmastra which is equitant to the atomic bomb (Fig.2). Many examples have been recounted by India's epic war happened during Mahabharata and Ramayana times indicate that our ancestors had the knowledge of nuclear energy. The descriptions of weapons such as pashupatastra, and brahmastra which could be able to destroy several thousand or trigger drought, could be imaginable in terms of nuclear weapons before thousands of years [12].

Fig.2: Brahmastra equivalent to atomic bomb mentioned during Mahabharata and Ramayana [12]

3.1.5 Artificial Intelligence, Robotics, and automata in Veda

Robotics and artificial intelligence are also somewhat related to the Vedic period-instrument. The "Samararingana sutradhara" (12th century) says: The females and males are designed for several kinds of automatic services. Their every part is made separately and fitted with pins and holes so that the eyes, hands, forearms, neck, thighs, wrists, and fingers can be functioned as per the needs. Yantra purusha or machine man who exists in the early era is just like a human being. The **Buddhistic bhaisajaya Vastu** when visited the home of yantracharya (teacher of mechanical engineering), met a machine girl who seemed like a human. She washed his feet, but could not speak. Yoga Vasistha describes human emotions, ego to Robots, and the application of AI (Artificial Intelligence). Sage Valmiki is credited as its author. It has 6 parts and in one of the parts, the application of Artificial Intelligence (A. I), human emotions, etc. to Robots are described. One Asura named **Sambarasura** had the power to raise himself in the sky and fight from outer space. Rig Veda clearly mentions that Asura does not mean "Demon". Asura means "the one who is not sura, or one who has magical or phenomenal powers (according to Rig Veda)". This Sambarasura created 3 robots using his technology and termed them dama, vyala, and kata [5].

During ancient time, the demon king Sambarasura created 3 robots and named them as "Dama", "KaTa", and "Vyala". Dama is derived from the root dam having the meaning to tame, subdue, conquer, and restrain of course the enemy). KaTa was like a modern tank used for protecting the army and Vyala means fierce, savage, cruel, and vicious like a snake or tiger. These robots were lifeless machines having no emotions and sentiments [5]. So they were never defeated in the war against

Adityas (gods). So later, Adityas played a trick to induce sentiments and emotions by introducing Artificial Intelligence into them. As a result, when again Adityas started fighting with these 3 robots and ran away with defeat caused induction of ego in the minds of these robots because the robots were thinking like humans due to this artificial intelligence. Adityas observed the drastically changed robots and so started manipulating those robots and said to them that because of their valour, Sambarasura always wins and enjoys his life at their cost. This statement washed robots' brains which added emotions and sentiments with them and hence, they forced to feel for enjoying their lives. They could not fight with the previous zeal which was obvious and finally defeated by Adityas. Modern-day robots have Artificial intelligence embedded into them. So there might be a chance that these robots can get ego and then they may rebel against mankind which may create difficulties to defeat them. So they may conquer mankind. But in that situation, man can follow the same trick as followed by the Gods.

3.1.6 Biomedical Instrumentation in the Vedic Period (Sushruta: 'The Father of Surgery)

Sushruta (also spelled as **Susruta** or Sushrutha) (6th century BC) who lived in ancient India was a surgeon and also the author of the book "**Sushruta Samhita**". In his book, he has classified human surgery in 8 categories, described over 120 surgical instruments, and 300 surgical procedures [13]. During his time, the health scientists conducted so many complicated surgeries like brain surgery, artificial limbs, caesareans, urinary stones, cataract, fractures, and even plastic surgery. Sushruta Samhita instruments are used in connection with a surgical operation. Some instruments are the Mandalagra, the Karapatra, the Vriddhipatra, the Nakhashastram, the Mudrika, the Utpalapatra, the Arddhadhara, the Suchi, the Kushapatra, the atemukha, the Shararimukha, the Antarmukha, the Trikurchaka, the Kutharika, the Vrihimukha, the Ara, the Vetasapatraka, the Vadisha, the Dantashanku, and the Eshani [14].

3.2.6.1 Surgical Instrument's Features and Characters

Instruments that are fitted with handles of easy grip and are made up of good and pure iron, well-shaped, sharp, and are set with edges that are not jagged should be treated as the best type of instruments. On the other hand, the unequal sharpness of the edge, rough-edginess incapable of cutting hair, over thickness or thinness, over lengthiness or shortness can be considered as defective traits in a surgical instrument. But a Karapatra set with a very rough edge may be used for bones' sawing. A surgical device intended for excision Bhedana has to be set with a side as thin as that of a Musura pulse lentil seed, while an instrument used in scraping has to be set with a side half as skinny as that of the former. The instruments used both in connection with the measures of secretion or reducing via uplifting (Vyadhana) need to be set with an edge as best as the human hair, and also at the same time as an instrument of the incision must have a side half of as thin as that of the former. The Surgical instruments need to be tempered with one of the 3 materials which include water, oil, and alkali. Instruments used in cutting an arrow, a bone, or any foreign matter (Shalya) pricked into the human body, should be tempered with alkali, while those which are made use in lopping off the flesh (from an affected part), cleaving, and cutting have to be tempered with water. Instruments used in cutting a vein or open a nerve need to be tempered with oil, and have to be whetted upon a species of stone-slab equivalent to a Masha pulse in colour, and their set-side must be covered via placing it in a sheath made from Shalmali wood [15].

Fig.3: Sushruta Performing Surgery [15]

3.1.7 Flight Instrumentation in Vedic period

Flight instruments are the instruments in the cockpit of an aircraft that provide the pilot with information. These are flight situations of that aircraft, such as vertical speed, airspeed, heading, altitude, and much other crucial information. They improve safety by allowing the pilot to fly the aircraft in level flight, and make turns, without a reference outside the aircraft such as the horizon. Vaimanika Shastra, which had been written in Vedic time was formed a part of the Rig Veda. Vaimanika Shastra, where it had been mentioned that the science of aircraft technology had already been worked on by Maharshi Bharadwaj was before 7000 years ago [16]. Fig.4 shows some examples of ancient Vimanas used during those Vedic periods.

(a) Tripura Vimana [17] (b) Rukma Vimana [17]

(c) Sundara Vimana [17] (d) Sakuna Vimana [17]

Fig.4: Sketch of Vedic planes used during ancient times as described in the book “Vyamanika”

Veda profound that, the people owned the flying machines called Vimanas during those eras. The ancient epic Ramayana described Vimana as double-deck, circular aircraft with portholes and a dome, much as we imaging a flying saucer. The pushpak Vimana of Ramayana is being quite popular. The "samara sutradhara" is a scientific treatise dealing with every possible angle of air travel in a

Vimana. There are 230 stanzas dealing with the construction, taking off, cruising for thousands of miles, normal and forced landing, and even collision of Vimanas with birds. The "Vemainik Shastra", describes these vimanas having speed of the wind and gave forth a melodious sound. In Treta Yuga, the greatest demon king of Lankacalled Lankapati Ravan was also used "Puspak Vimana" for kidnapping goddess Sita [12].

3.1.8 Invention of Portable Battery, Electric City Dry cell during Ancient Vedic Period

The country India has given birth to many great Munis and rishis who were the great inventors and masters of all science and technologies before thousands of years ago. Out of those great rishis, one was rishi Agastya who was the master of Vedas and Samhitas. Rishi Agastya wrote a book named Agastya Samhita which describes the method of making an electric battery, and that water can be split into oxygen and hydrogen. The modern battery cell resembles Agastya's method of generating electricity. For generating electricity, Sage Agastya had used the following material [18]:

- 1) Copper Plate, 2) Copper Sulphate, 3) Zinc Amalgam, 4) One earthen Pot, 5) Wet Saw Dust

Fig.5: Dry Electric Cell described in Agastya Samhita [18]

His shloka which is written in Sanskrit says:

संस्थाप्य मृण्मये पात्रे ताम्रपत्रं सुसंस्कृतम्।
छादयेच्छिखिग्रीवेन चार्दाभिः॥काष्ठापांसुभिः दस्तालोष्टो निधात्वय।:पारदाच्छादितस्ततः।
संयोगाज्जायते तेजो मित्रावरुणसंज्ञितम्॥

In English font:

“Sansthapya Mrinmaya Patre Tamrapatram Susanskritam.
Chhadyechhikhigriiven Chardrabhih Kashthpamsubhih.
Dastaloshto Nidhatavyah Pardachhaditastah
Sanyogajjayte Tejo Mitravarusangyitam” [18].

Which means, “Place a well-cleaned copper plate in an earthenware vessel. Cover it first by copper sulfate and then by moist sawdust. After that, put a mercury-amalgamated zinc sheet on top of the sawdust to avoid polarization. The contact will produce an energy known by the twin name of Mitra-Varuna. Water will be split by this current into Pranavayu and Udanavayu. A chain of one hundred jars is said to give a very effective force. (p. 422)”

When a cell was prepared according to Agastya Samhita and measured, it gives open-circuit voltage as 1.138 volts, and short circuit current as 23 mA.

Anen Jalbhangosti Prano Daneshu Vayushu Evam Shatanam Kumbhanamsanyogkaryakritsmritah. [18].

That means if we use the power of 100 earthen pots on water, then water will change its form into life-giving oxygen and floating hydrogen.

Vayubandhakvastren Nibaddho Yanmastake
Udanah Swalaghutve Bibhartyakashayanakam. [18].

It means if hydrogen is contained in an airtight cloth, it can be used in aerodynamics, i.e. it will fly in the air. (Today's Hydrogen Balloon)

Fig.6: Ancient India Battery as designed by rishi Agastya [18]

Process of Electroplating by Maharshi Agastya in Agastya Sanhita

(Excerpt from “Technology of the Gods: The Incredible Sciences of the Ancients” – By David Hatcher Childress)

The London Protestant Mission’s reverend, S. Mateer saw a great lamp lighted over in a deep well, inside the temple since one hundred and twenty years ago. The background of Agastya Samhitas text gives precise directions for constructing electrical batteries, and this speculation is not extravagant.

3.1.9 Electrical Energy in Veda

In Veda, the electricity is mentioned by the name Indra and Vidyuta. Except this, Atharvaveda (2.5.12) refers to two sorts of electricity i.e. positive and negative along with its friendly and damaging nature [19]. According to Ayurveda (1.16.5), the electricity is hidden within the water and once it comes out; it spreads light and provides energy. Ayurveda (1.85.5; 188.1) describes the use of electricity in weapons and telegraphy [20]. Electricity can be generated from energy as stated in Rig veda.1.45.5.

4. CONCLUSION

The technology and working principle of the different electronic-based instruments used is somewhat related to modern time instruments which show that in the Vedic period, India leads the world in terms of technology and having the least side effects. All those in modern scientists and researchers from across the world invented various advanced instruments, but it could be termed as an up-gradation of instruments discovered by India in the Vedic period. The instruments of the Vedic period were equipped with environment-friendly, reliability and value-oriented which has substantial capability to smooth operation in usual friendly compared to modern instruments. Indian Rishis and

Munis efforts and contribution towards the development of the society can never be forgettable in any period. So the scientists and researchers of this present era will always recall theories and concepts of Veda and also will make an effort to shape it in a new way. For example, India's premier defence research agency, DRDO (Defence Research Development Organization) has gone right ahead to sign a memorandum of understanding with the TTD (Tirumala Tirupati Devasthanam) to conduct scientific research on the Vedas to scout for possible secrets on missile technologies hidden in the ancient scriptures. The MoU with TTD was signed by the Hyderabad-based Research Centre Imarat (RCI)-DRDO to conduct scientific research on the Vedas. The Hyderabad-based Research Centre, Imarat (RCI)-DRDO has an inertial instrumentation laboratory, full-scale environmental and electronic warfare test facilities, a state-of-the-art missile integration checkout centre. TTD directly supports 100 Vedic schools across India that will translate the Vedic technology written in Veda and will submit it to the DRDO. These above are just a few examples of using the knowledge-ocean of Veda. Thus it can be said that optimum and systematic exploration of Vedic knowledge would be helpful in Technocrats and scientists to deadlock words in a better way which would be nature friendly, sustainable, and equitable for nature as well human beings.

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